

Bioprospecting of Culturable Halophilic Bacteria Isolated from Mediterranean Solar Saltern for Extracellular Halotolerant Enzymes

Ahmed Mohamed Ali¹, Tahany M.A. Abdel-Rahman¹, and Mohamed G. Farahat^{1,2*}

¹Botany and Microbiology Department, Faculty of Science, Cairo University, Giza 12613, Egypt

²Biotechnology Department, Faculty of Nanotechnology for Postgraduate Studies, Sheikh Zayed Branch Campus, Cairo University, Sheikh Zayed City, Giza 12588, Egypt

Received: January 19, 2024 / Revised: February 29, 2024 / Accepted: March 7, 2024

Halophilic bacteria are promising reservoirs for halotolerant enzymes that have gained much attention in biotechnological applications due to their remarkable activity and stability. In this study, 62 halophilic bacterial strains isolated from a solar saltern were screened for the production of various extracellular enzymes. The results revealed that 31 strains (50%) were positive for amylase production while 26 strains (41.9%) were positive for protease. Further, 22 strains (35.48%) exhibited β -glucosidase activity and only 17 (27.41%) demonstrated lipase activity. Of the investigated halophiles, ten strains growing in the presence of $\geq 15\%$ NaCl (w/v) were selected and identified based on their 16S rRNA gene sequences as *Halomonas meridiana*, *Salinivibrio costicola*, *Virgibacillus oceani*, *Virgibacillus marismortui*, *Marinobacter lipolyticus*, *Halobacillus karajensis*, *Salicola salis*, *Pseudoalteromonas shioyasakiensis*, *Salinicoccus amylolyticus*, and *Paracoccus salipaludis*. Therefore, the present study highlights the diversity of the culturable halophilic bacteria in a Mediterranean solar saltern, harboring various valuable halotolerant enzymes.

Keywords: Halophilic bacteria, solar salterns, hydrolytic enzymes, bacterial diversity

Introduction

Microorganisms have various adaptive strategies to tolerate environmental stresses, especially extremophiles which can survive under adverse conditions, such as high temperature, pH, and salinity [1]. This can be achieved by many mechanisms including the ability to produce particular secondary metabolites, which have many applications in various industrial fields and biotechnological research [2]. Extremophilic microorganisms that are capable of surviving in high salinity can grow in habitats such as the Dead Sea, solar salterns, and salt lakes. These organisms can produce extracellular enzymes with potential interest in several biotechnological

and industrial applications due to their high activity and stability at low water levels [1, 3, 4]. It was reported that halophiles-derived enzymes were active under extreme conditions because their surfaces carry a high number of amino acid residues of negative charges [5]. Hydrolytic enzymes such as proteases, lipases, β -glucosidase, inulinases, cellulases, and amylases received increased attention due to their significant industrial roles in wastewater treatment, biosynthetic processes, agriculture, medicine, foods, detergent, textile, paper, and bio-fuel industries [6–10]. Also, hydrolytic enzymes have crucial roles in bioremediation processes and biodegradation of pollutants [11–14]. In this context, various bacteria strains isolated from marine habitats were reported as promising sources for a wide range of significant commercial hydrolytic enzymes including cellulases, nucleases, inulinases, xylanases, amylases, galactosidases,

*Corresponding author
E-mail: farahat@cu.edu.eg

glucosidases, lipases, chitinases, dextranases, proteases, etc. [15–20]. Amylases are classified as hydrolyzing enzymes that hydrolyze starch into monosaccharide units by acting on its α -1,4-glucosidic linkages [21, 22]. Various amylases were applied in industrial sectors for starch liquefaction, biomasses saccharification, fabrics desizing, beverage fermentation, and syrups production [23, 24]. In this regard, α -amylase from the marine bacterium *Bacillus subtilis* S8-18 was used to inhibit/disrupt the biofilms of some human bacterial pathogens such as against methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and *Vibrio cholerae* [25]. Also, α -amylase from halophilic *Streptomyces* sp. has been used for hydrolysis of agro-wastes [26]. The enzyme derived from *Bacillus tequilensis* TB5 is used as a laundry additive and as a textile desizer [27]. Microorganisms that are isolated from environments with high salt concentrations have been reported as a prolific source for the production of amylases such as *Halomonas meridiana* [28] and *Zunongwangia profunda* [29]. In addition, proteases are one of the economically important enzymes involved in the hydrolysis of proteins into small peptides and/or free amino acids by acting on peptide linkages [30]. These enzymes have many applications in the leather industry, textiles, food processing, and dairy production [31, 32].

Furthermore, the halophilic *Bacillus* sp. strain SP II-4 has been reported as a significant producer of alkaline protease which demonstrated better content lens cleansing efficiency along with common chemical disinfectant [33]. Protease from a marine bacterium, *Bacillus tequilensis* P15, has industrial applications such as removing of blood stains from fabrics, stripping off the gelatin from used photographic films, and dehairing of hide [34]. Also, the halotolerant protease produced by *Halobacillus andaensis* has been used for the production of bioactive peptides from fish muscle protein [35]. Halotolerant proteases have been reported to be able to remove recalcitrant blood and egg stains, and are used in the leather industry as dehairing agents at high salt conditions [36]. Microorganisms from hypersaline habitats have been reported as a significant source of protease, such as *Halococcus agarilyticus* [37] and *Lysinibacillus fusiformis* sp. [38]. Furthermore, lipases that hydrolyze fat into glycerol and fatty acids play a significant role in various industrial fields such as biodiesel, foods and drinks,

leather, detergents, and pharmaceuticals [39]. Marine-derived lipases exhibited high activity under adverse conditions, so marine microorganisms have been reported as prolific sources for producing marine lipases [40–42]. Lipase derived from halophilic microorganisms has been reported as an prominent enzyme in food industries, including baking and brewing, omega-3 production, natural sweeteners, and food processing [43]. Lipase from *Staphylococcus warneri* is used in fish sauce production to enhance the flavor [44]. In addition, lipase derived from *Marinobacter lipolyticus* SM19 has been used in the pharmaceuticals and food industry through the synthesis of polyunsaturated fatty acids from fish oil [45]. In the medical field, a halothermostable lipase from *Oceanobacillus* sp. PUMB02 was used to disrupt biofilm against different food pathogens such as *Listeria* sp., *Bacillus* sp., *Serratia* sp., and *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* [46]. It has been suggested that halotolerant lipases are promising candidates to be applied in bioremediation processes. Cold active lipases from *Pseudoalteromonas* sp. are used in the bioremediation of aqueous systems contaminated with oil and in detergent formulations [47], and lipase from *Halomonas* sp. C2SS100 showed the ability to remove of lubricating oil stains from polycotton [48]. Many halophilic bacteria have been documented as promising sources for the production of lipases such as *Halobacillus truperi* [49] and *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* [50]. Moreover, β -glucosidase is a hydrolyzing enzyme that catalyzes the release of non-reducing terminal glucosidic residues from glycosylated metabolites or oligosaccharides and has various applications in the food, chemical, and pharmaceutical industries for the production of Gardinia Blue (natural pigment), gentiooligosaccharides, and bioconversion of polydatin to resveratrol [51]. In the food industry, β -glucosidases maintain the food flavor [52–54]. Halophilic β -glucosidase from *Pseudoalteromonas* has been used in industrial production and food processing due to its significant activity toward isoflavones [55]. Also, this enzyme is involved in the synthesis of various compounds like glycoconjugates and oligosaccharides [56]. In the present study, we addressed the diversity of culturable halophilic bacteria isolated from Mediterranean solar saltern and investigated their ability to produce various extracellular hydrolytic enzymes.

Material and Methods

Sample Collection

Sediments and brine samples were collected from a solar saltern, in Egypt (30°59'24.9"N 29°37'00.4"E) in sterile plastic bags and transferred to the laboratory through a short time after sampling and surveyed immediately for bacterial isolation.

Isolation of Halophilic Bacteria

Isolation of halophilic bacteria was performed using tryptic soy agar medium (TSA, Condalab, Spain) supplemented with 10% (w/v) NaCl. In brief, 100 µl of each collected sample were plated and the inoculated plates were incubated at 37°C and checked daily for up to 7 days. The recovered colonies were transferred on new agar plates and sub-cultured many times until pure cultures were obtained. For the preservation of bacterial isolates, stocks of 20% glycerol of pure cultures were prepared and stored at -80°C.

Screening for Extracellular Hydrolytic Enzymes

Amylase activity. The potential of halophilic isolates for amylase production was investigated using starch agar medium containing (g/l): yeast extract, 1; peptone, 5; soluble starch, 2; agar, 20; supplemented with 10% NaCl. After incubation at 37°C for 3–5 days, plates were flooded with iodine-potassium iodide solution. The formation of a clear zone around the bacterial colonies was recorded as starch hydrolysis [57].

Protease activity. The proteolytic activity was assessed by the method described by [57] with some modifications. Each strain was inoculated on skim milk agar medium containing (g/l): skim milk, 20; glucose, 1; tryptone, 5; yeast extract, 2.5; agar, 20; supplemented with 10% NaCl. After incubation at 37°C for 5 days, the plates were checked. The appearance of a clear zone around indicates protease activity.

Lipase activity. The investigation of lipase activity was conducted using a screening medium containing (g/l): peptone, 10; CaCl₂·2H₂O, 0.1; agar, 20, supplemented with 10% NaCl (w/v). After autoclaving, sterile tween 80 was added to a final concentration of 1% (v/v). Each bac-

terial strain was inoculated and the plates were incubated at 37°C for 4–5 days. Subsequently, the appearance of white precipitate around the bacterial growth indicated the lipase activity [58].

β-Glucosidase activity. The β-glucosidase activity was inspected using TSA medium containing (g/l): beef extract, 3; peptone, 5; agar, 20, supplemented with 10% NaCl, 0.05% esculin and 0.01% ferric citrate. The formation of a brown-black zone around the bacterial colonies after incubation at 37°C for 5 days indicated β-glucosidase activity [51].

Salinity Tolerance

All isolated strains were inoculated in tryptic soy broth supplemented with different concentrations of NaCl (10, 15, 20 and 25%) and incubated at 37°C in a shaking incubator (140 rpm). The cultures were checked daily for bacterial growth up to 15 days.

Molecular Identification and Phylogenetic Analysis

Extraction of genomic DNA from bacterial isolates was performed by using GeneJET™ Genomic DNA Purification Kit according to the manufacturer protocol. Amplification of nearly full-length 16S rRNA gene was conducted by PCR using universal primers, 27F (AGAGTTTGATCMTGGCTCAG) and 1492R (TACGGY-TACCTTGTTACGACTT) [59]. Afterward, the amplicons were purified and sequenced using ABI 3730xI sequence analyzer (Applied Biosystems, USA), and the sequences were analyzed using the Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/blast>). Construction of the phylogenetic tree was performed using the Neighbor-joining method based on bootstrap values (1000 replications with MEGAX software). The sequences of the 16S rRNA gene were deposited in the GenBank.

Results

Isolation of Halophilic Bacteria

In the present study, 62 halophilic bacterial strains were isolated on TSA medium supplemented with 10% NaCl, from a solar saltern, in Egypt. After that, all isolated halophiles were screened for the production of various extracellular hydrolytic enzymes.

Screening of Extracellular Hydrolytic Enzymes

All isolated bacterial halophiles were screened for their ability to produce four extracellular hydrolytic enzymes (amylase, protease, lipase, and β -glucosidase) in the presence of 10% NaCl. Of the investigated strains, 54/62 (87.09%) were positive for at least one extracellular enzyme. On the other hand, eight strains (12.91%) did not produce any of the investigated extracellular enzymes. Results showed that 31 strains (50%) had amylase activity (Fig. 1A). Regarding the protease activity, 26 strains (41.9%) exhibited proteolytic activity on skimmed milk agar plates (Fig. 1B). Seventeen strains (27.41%) showed lipase activity (Fig. 1C) and 22 halo-

Fig. 1. Screening of extracellular enzyme production. (A) amylase, (B) protease, (C) lipase, and (D) β -galactosidase of the selected halophilic bacteria.

Fig. 2. Venn diagram shows prevalence of extracellular amylase, protease, lipase, and β -galactosidase.

philic strains (35.48%) were found to produce dark brown zones around their colonies, indicating β -glucosidase activity (Fig. 1D). Results revealed that only three bacterial strains were positive for all investigated enzymes and seven strains produced three different enzymes. Moreover, 19 bacterial strains exhibited positive activity for two investigated enzymes, and 25 strains exhibited activity for only one enzyme (Fig. 2).

Salinity Tolerance

Bacterial growth in different concentrations of NaCl (10–25%, w/v) was investigated. All the investigated isolates exhibited significant growth at 10% NaCl. Results revealed that three strains (SHB1, SHB21 and SHB59) were able to grow at NaCl concentrations up to 25%, while SHB7, SHB26 and SHB37 exhibited growth up to 20% NaCl. Three strains (SHB13, SHB22, SHB55 and SHB60) showed growth up to 15% NaCl (Table 1). Among 62 halophilic strains, 10 exhibiting the ability to grow in high salt concentrations ($\geq 15\%$) were selected while 52 strains that did not grow on more than 10% NaCl were maintained at -80°C for future investigations. The selected strains were subjected to molecular identification based on 16S rRNA analysis.

Molecular Identification and Phylogenetic Analysis

Based on 16S rRNA gene analysis, the selected halophilic strains were identified as *Halomonas meridiana*, *Salinivibrio costicola*, *Virgibacillus oceani*, *Virgibacillus*

Table 1. Salinity tolerance of halophilic strains isolated from a Mediterranean solar saltern located at the northern coast of Egypt.

Strain	Growth with NaCl (% w/v)			
	10	15	20	25
SHB1	+	+	+	+
SHB7	+	+	+	-
SHB13	+	+	-	-
SHB21	+	+	+	+
SHB22	+	+	-	-
SHB26	+	+	+	-
SHB37	+	+	+	-
SHB55	+	+	-	-
SHB59	+	+	+	+
SHB60	+	+	-	-

'+' positive for the test, '-' negative for the test.

Table 2. Identification of extreme halophilic bacterial strains based on 16S rRNA gene sequence analysis.

Strain	Accession Number	Closest Species	Similarity (%)
SHB1	PP035898	<i>Halomonas meridiana</i>	99.93
SHB7	OR616804	<i>Salinivibrio costicola</i>	99.30
SHB13	OR616805	<i>Virgibacillus oceani</i>	99.79
SHB21	OR616806	<i>Virgibacillus marismortui</i>	99.87
SHB22	OR616807	<i>Marinobacter lipolyticus</i>	99.86
SHB26	OR616808	<i>Halobacillus karajensis</i>	99.79
SHB37	OR616809	<i>Salicola salis</i>	99.64
SHB55	OR616810	<i>Pseudoalteromonas shioyasakiensis</i>	99.78
SHB59	OR616811	<i>Salinicoccus amylolyticus</i>	99.55
SHB60	OR616812	<i>Paracoccus salipaludis</i>	99.77

marismortui, *Marinobacter lipolyticus*, *Halobacillus karajensis*, *Salicola salis*, *Pseudoalteromonas shioyasakiensis*, *Salinicoccus amylolyticus* and *Paracoccus salipaludis*. Sequences of the 16S rRNA gene were submitted to the GenBank and the accession numbers were assigned (Table 2). The Neighbor-joining phylogenetic tree was constructed based on 16S rRNA gene sequences of the bacterial isolates (Fig. 3).

Concerning the selected bacterial strains, results revealed that ten identified strains activity of possess at least one hydrolytic enzyme (Table 3). The most active strain that exhibited activity of all tested enzymes was *H. karajensis* SHB26, while *M. lipolyticus* SHB22 produced lipase only. Furthermore, *V. oceani* SHB13, *S.*

Fig. 3. Neighbor-joining phylogenetic tree based on 16S rRNA gene sequences showing the relationship between the selected strains and the most closely related species.

Table 3. Extracellular hydrolytic enzymes of extreme halophilic bacteria.

Strain	Extracellular Enzyme			
	Amylase	Protease	Lipase	β -Glucosidase
<i>H. meridiana</i> SHB1	+	-	+	-
<i>S. costicola</i> SHB7	+	-	+	-
<i>V. oceani</i> SHB13	-	+	+	+
<i>V. marismortui</i> SHB21	-	+	-	+
<i>M. lipolyticus</i> SHB22	-	-	+	-
<i>H. karajensis</i> SHB26	+	+	+	+
<i>S. salis</i> SHB37	+	+	+	-
<i>P. shioyasakiensis</i> SHB55	+	+	-	+
<i>S. amylolyticus</i> SHB59	+	-	-	+
<i>P. salipaludis</i> SHB60	-	+	+	-

'+' positive for the test, '-' negative for the test.

salis SHB37, and *P. shioyasakiensis* SHB55 exhibited the activity of 3 enzymes, while *H. meridiana* SHB1, *S. costicola* SHB7, *V. marismortui* SHB21, *S. amylolyticus* SHB59, and *P. salipaludis* SHB60 secreted two enzymes.

Discussion

Recently, halophilic bacteria have been regarded as prolific sources of novel economically important stable enzymes that are functional under extreme conditions. Due to their unique properties, halophilic-derived enzymes are extensively used in many industrial fields. In the present work, 62 halophilic bacteria were isolated from a solar saltern in Egypt among them ten halophilic strains that can grow at NaCl concentrations equal to or more than 15% belonging to nine genera were selected. Because of operating at high salt concentrations with the reducing water activity, enzymes from the extreme halophilic microorganisms exhibit extraordinary stability and are thought to be robust biocatalysts in aqueous/organic and nonaqueous media with superior activity in various biotechnological applications [60, 61]. Solar salterns are one of the natural habitats that are characterized by the presence of high salt concentrations and have been reported as a rich source for the isolation of halophilic microorganisms. In a similar study, various halophilic bacteria have been isolated from solar salterns in

Tunisia, including *Halomonas* sp., *Salinivibrio* sp., *Cobetia* sp., *Idiomarina* sp., and *Marinobacter* [62]. Also, 28 halophilic bacteria have been isolated from Indian solar salterns which belonged to seven genera: *Stenotrophomonas*, *Staphylococcus*, *Bacillus*, *Enterobacter*, *Pseudomonas*, *Oceanobacillus* and *Ochrabactrum* [63] and ten bacterial halophiles have been isolated from hypersaline habitats in Morocco, nine bacterial strains belonged to *Halomonas* genus and one bacterial strain belonged to *Marinobacter* genus [64]. Furthermore, 17 bacterial isolates have been isolated from a hypersaline lake in the Northwest of Algeria, which belong to three genera: *Virgibacillus*, *Bacillus*, and *Halomonas* [65]. Moreover, *Providencia stuartii* sp. and *Lysinibacillus fusiformis* sp. were isolated from high-salt environments [38]. From saltern ponds in Trapani, Sicily, *Halomonas* sp., *Salinibacter ruber*, and *Brevibacterium* sp. have been isolated [66]. Various bacterial and archaeal halophiles were isolated from a hypersaline lake in the south of Tunisia, and identified as *Salicola* sp., *Bacillus* sp., *Halorubrum* sp., *Natrinema* sp., *Haloterrigena* sp. [67], and *Pseudoalteromonas* sp. DL-6 has been isolated from marine sediments in the Chinese Bohai Sea [68]. Bacterial isolates related to genera: *Brevibacterium*, *Chromohalobacter*, *Virgibacillus*, *Halomonas*, *Salinivibrio*, *Nesiotobacter*, *Cobetia*, and *Salinicoccus* have been isolated from solar salterns in Bulgaria [69]. In a similar study that investigated the halophilic bacteria from a solar saltern located in the Mediterranean Sea (Sfax, Tunisia), 40 halophilic isolates were identified based on phylogenetic analysis of 16S rRNA gene sequences. Their diversity showed that 4 strains (10%) were belonging to *Firmicutes* and 36 strains (90%) were belonging to *Gamma-Proteobacteria*. The *Gamma-Proteobacteria* consisted of various subgroups of the *Alcanivoracaceae* (5%), the *Idiomarinaceae* (7.5%), the *Alteromonadaceae* (10%), the *Vibrionaceae* (15%) and the *Halomonadaceae* (52.5%) [70]. In agreement with our results, halophilic bacteria such as *Halomonas*, *Salicola*, *Halovibrio*, and *Salinibacter* have been isolated from solar salterns in Baja California, Mexico [71]. Also, *Marinococcus*, *Salinibacter*, and *Cytophaga* were isolated from solar salterns of Tamil Nadu, India [72]. Furthermore, similar halophilic bacteria such as *Salinibacter ruber*, *Brevibacterium* sp. and *Halomonas* sp. have been isolated from saltern ponds of Trapani, Sicily [66], and *Salinivibrio kushneri*

has been isolated from salterns, Spain [73]. Although many species belonging to the recovered genera have been described in previous studies, our findings spotlighted the diversity of these strains with emphasis on their extracellular enzymatic activity.

In the present study, amylase was the most prevalent enzyme followed by protease, while lipase was the least prevalent enzyme. The ten extreme halophilic identified strains showed at least one activity of the tested enzymes. The most active strain that showed activity of the four enzymes was *H. karajensis*, while *M. lipolyticus* produced lipase only. Meanwhile, *V. oceani*, *S. salis*, and *P. shioyasakiensis* exhibited the activity of three enzymes, but isolates such as *H. meridiana*, *S. costicola*, *V. marismortui*, *S. amylolyticus*, and *P. salipaludis* exhibited activity of two enzymes. Similarly, *Salicola* sp., *Bacillus* sp., *Halorubrum* sp., *Natrinema* sp., and *Haloterrigena* sp. isolated from hypersaline lake in the south of Tunisia, were screened for the activity of hydrolytic enzymes, including protease, amylase, cellulase, lipase, xylanase, and pectinase and found that most these isolates exhibited significant activity of the tested enzymes [67]. It has been suggested that marine halophilic microorganisms, classified as one class of extremophiles, are an extraordinary source of new enzymes involved in the bioremediation of toxic pollutants and dye decolorization [74, 75]. Our findings revealed amylase production by six halophilic strains, namely *H. meridiana*, *S. costicola*, *H. karajensis*, *S. salis*, *P. shioyasakiensis*, and *S. amylolyticus*. On the other hand, *V. oceani*, *V. marismortui*, *M. lipolyticus*, and *P. salipaludis* showed no amylase activity. In good agreement, bacterial strains isolated from saline habitats showed significant amylase activity, such as *Halobacillus* sp. [76], and *Pseudoalteromonas* sp. M175 [77]. About 58 strains of *Vibrio* spp. isolated from marine habitats in Malaysia exhibited amylase activity [15]. Furthermore, amylase production by numerous microorganisms isolated from saline and hypersaline habitats has been well documented, such as *Bacillus subtilis* S8-1 [78], *Streptomyces* sp. D1 [79], *Vibrio* sp. [80], *Wangia* sp. C52 [81], *Pontibacillus chungwhensis* [82], *Bacillus barbaricus* [82], *Nocardioopsis* sp. B2 [83], and *Anoxybacillus beppuensis* TSSC-1 [84]. In this study, we identified six protease-producing halophilic strains, *V. oceani*, *V. marismortui*, *H. karajensis*, *S. salis*, *P. shioyasakiensis*, and *P. salipaludis*. Similarly,

previous studies have reported the production of proteases from bacterial strains isolated from habitats with high salinity, such as *Pseudoalteromonas* sp. strain CP76 [85], *Halobacillus karajensis* [86], *Virgibacillus marismortui* [87], *Virgibacillus* sp. EMB13 [88], *Halobacillus* sp. CJ4 [89], *Virgibacillus* sp. SK33 [90], *Halobacillus* sp. LY6 [91], *Salicola* sp. IC10 [92], *Halobacillus* sp. SCSIO 20089 [93], as well as *Halobacillus andaensis*, *H. dabanensis* and *Salicola marasensis* [94]. Similarly, various halophilic and halotolerant bacteria have been reported as significant producers of protease such as *Halococcus agarilyticus* [37], *Bacillus* sp. [95], *Bacillus firmus* CAS 7 [96], and *Pseudomonas* SD11 [97]. Our findings harmony with those of previous studies that reported the absence of extracellular protease activity in various species belonging to the genus *Salinivibrio*, such as *Salinivibrio costicola* NCIMB 13595 and *Salinicoccus roseus* DSM 5351 [98].

In this investigation, we identified seven promising lipase-producing halophilic bacterial strains: *H. meridiana*, *S. costicola*, *V. oceani*, *M. lipolyticus*, *H. karajensis*, *S. salis*, and *P. salipaludis*. Whereas *V. marismortui*, *P. shioyasakiensis*, and *S. amylolyticus* exhibited no lipase activity. Likewise, various bacterial strains recovered from saline or hypersaline habitats displayed significant lipase production, such as *Marinobacter lipolytica* [45], *Marinobacter* sp. EMB5 [99], *Marinobacter adhaerens* t76_800 [100], *Haloarcula* sp. G41 [101], *Aeromonas* sp. EBB-1 [102], *Vibrio* sp. [103], *Vibrio vulnificus* [104], *Salinivibrio costicola* DSM 8285 [98], *Salinivibrio costicola* NCIMB 13595 [98], *Halobacillus* sp. strain AR11 [49], *Halobacillus trueperi* RSK CAS9 [105], *Virgibacillus alimentarius* [106], *Salicola* sp. IC10 [92], and *Salicola marasensis* [94]. Hydrolysis by β -glucosidase is considered a significant step in the hydrolysis of lignocellulosic materials [107] by cellulases that hydrolyze cellulose into simple units by cleaving β -1,4-glycosidic linkages [108, 109]. These enzymes are classified into three types; exoglucanases, endoglucanases, and β -glucosidases [110]. For β -glucosidase, we identified five promising producers: *V. oceani*, *V. marismortui*, *H. karajensis*, *P. shioyasakiensis* and *S. amylolyticus*. However, *H. meridiana*, *S. costicola*, *M. lipolyticus*, *S. salis*, and *P. salipaludis* did not exhibit extracellular β -glucosidase activity. In this connection, *Pseudoalteromonas* sp. GXQ-1 showed significant activity of β -glucosidase [55]. Moreover, many

marine-derived bacteria have been reported as a significant source for the production of β -glucosidase such as *Streptomyces* sp.

In conclusion, this investigation shed light on the diversity of halophilic bacterial strains from the extreme ecosystem, Mediterranean solar saltern in Egypt. The majority of the recovered halophilic strains were able to produce salt-tolerant hydrolytic enzymes. We found that amylase was the most prevalent enzyme, while lipase was uncommon. Furthermore, ten extreme halophilic bacterial strains belonging to nine genera were identified. Of these strains, *H. meridiana* SHB1, *V. marismortui* SHB21, and *S. amylolyticus* SHB59 showed remarkable growth in the presence of 25% NaCl and produced at least two halotolerant extracellular enzymes. Nonetheless, future studies are planned to purify and characterize these enzymes to exploit their merits in various industrial applications.

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no financial conflicts of interest to declare.

References

- Thakur N, Singh SP, Zhang C. 2022. Microorganisms under extreme environments and their applications. *Curr. Res. Microb. Sci.* **3**: 100141.
- Henrique RP. 2013. Extremophiles and extreme environments. *Life* **3**: 482-485.
- Didari M, Bagheri M, Amoozegar MA, Bouzari S, Babavalian H, Tebyanian H, et al. 2020. Diversity of halophilic and halotolerant bacteria in the largest seasonal hypersaline lake (Aran-Bidgol-Iran). *J. Environ. Health Sci. Eng.* **18**: 961-971.
- Nwankwo C, Hou J, Cui HL. 2023. Extracellular proteases from halophiles: diversity and application challenges. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **107**: 5923-5934.
- Farahat MG, Amr D, Galal A. 2020. Molecular cloning, structural modeling and characterization of a novel glutaminase-free L-asparaginase from *Cobetia amphilecti* AM16. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **143**: 685-695.
- Singh RS, Chauhan K, Kennedy JF. 2017. A panorama of bacterial inulinases: production, purification, characterization and industrial applications. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **96**: 312-322.
- Ariaeenejad S, Kavousi K, Han JL, Ding XZ, Hosseini Salekdeh G. 2023. Efficiency of an alkaline, thermostable, detergent compatible, and organic solvent tolerant lipase with hydrolytic potential in biotreatment of wastewater. *Sci. Total Environ.* **866**: 161066.
- Thapa S, Li H, OHair J, Bhatti S, Chen FC, Nasr K AI, et al. 2019. Biochemical characteristics of microbial enzymes and their significance from industrial perspectives. *Mol. Biotechnol.* **61**: 579-601.
- Ramasamy R, Subramanian RB. 2022. Enzyme hydrolysis of polyester knitted fabric: A method to control the microfiber shedding from synthetic textile. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* **29**: 81265-81278.
- Sui B, Wang T, Fang J, Hou Z, Shu T, Lu Z, et al. 2023. Recent advances in the biodegradation of polyethylene terephthalate with cutinase-like enzymes. *Front. Microbiol.* **14**: 1265139.
- Wang J, Liu Y, Ma Y, Wang X, Zhang B. 2023. Research progress regarding the role of halophilic and halotolerant microorganisms in the eco-environmental sustainability and conservation. *J. Clean. Prod.* **418**: 138054.
- Jafari N, Rezaei S, Rezaei R, Dilmaghani H. 2017. Improved production and characterization of a highly stable laccase from the halophilic bacterium *Chromohalobacter salexigens* for the efficient delignification of almond shell bio-waste. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **105**: 489-498.
- Zhou M, Dong B, Shao Z. 2020. Complete genome sequence of *Marinobacter* sp. LQ44, a haloalkaliphilic phenol-degrading bacterium isolated from a deep-sea hydrothermal vent. *Mar. Genom.* **50**: 100697.
- Fan S, Li K, Yan Y, Wang J, Wang J, Qiao C, et al. 2018. A novel chlorpyrifos hydrolase CPD from *Paracoccus* sp. TRP: Molecular cloning, characterization and catalytic mechanism. *Electron. J. Biotechnol.* **31**: 10-16.
- Cheng TH, Ismail N, Kamaruding N, Saidin J, Danish-Daniel M. 2020. Industrial enzymes-producing marine bacteria from marine resources. *Biotechnol. Rep.* **27**: e00482.
- Ren W, Wu H, Guo C, Xue B, Long H, Zhang X, et al. 2021. Multi-strain tropical *Bacillus* spp. as a potential probiotic biocontrol agent for large-scale enhancement of mariculture water quality. *Front. Microbiol.* **12**: 699378.
- Wei Y, Bu J, Long H, Zhang X, Cai X, Huang A, et al. 2021. Community structure of protease-producing bacteria cultivated from aquaculture systems: Potential impact of a tropical environment. *Front. Microbiol.* **12**: 638129.
- Menasria T, Monteoliva-Sánchez M, Benhadj M, Benammar L, Boukoucha M, Aguilera M. 2022. Unraveling the enzymatic and antibacterial potential of rare halophilic actinomycetes from Algerian hypersaline wetland ecosystems. *J. Basic Microbiol.* **62**: 1202-1215.
- Yousefi-Mokri M, Sharafi A, Rezaei S, Sadeghian-Abadi S, Imanparast S, Mogharabi-Manzari M, et al. 2019. Enzymatic hydrolysis of inulin by an immobilized extremophilic inulinase from the halophile bacterium *Alkalibacillus filiformis*. *Carbohydr. Res.* **483**: 107746.
- Farahat MG, Shehata HM, Kamel Z. 2020. Codon optimization and co-expression of thermostable β -galactosidase and L-arabinose isomerase in *Lactococcus lactis* for single-step production of food-grade D-tagatose. *Biochem. Cell. Arch.* **20**: 2545-2552.
- Aarti C, Khusro A, Agastian P, Darwish NM, Al DA. 2020. Molecular

- diversity and hydrolytic enzymes production abilities of soil bacteria. *Saudi J. Biol. Sci.* **27**: 3235-3248.
22. Khusro A, Aarti C. 2015. Molecular identification of newly isolated *Bacillus* strains from poultry farm and optimization of process parameters for enhanced production of extracellular amylase using OFAT method. *Res. J. Microbiol.* **10**: 393.
 23. Farooq MA, Ali S, Hassan A, Tahir HM, Mumtaz S, Mumtaz S. 2021. Biosynthesis and industrial applications of α -amylase: a review. *Arch. Microbiol.* **203**: 1281-1292.
 24. Rathod BG, Pandala S, Poosarla VG. 2023. A novel halo-acid-alkali-tolerant and surfactant stable amylase secreted from halophile *Bacillus siamensis* F2 and its application in waste valorization by bioethanol production and food industry. *Appl. Biochem. Biotechnol.* **195**: 4775-4795.
 25. Kalpana BJ, Aarthi S, Pandian SK. 2012. Antibiofilm activity of α -amylase from *Bacillus subtilis* S8-18 against biofilm forming human bacterial pathogens. *Appl. Biochem. Biotechnol.* **167**: 1778-1794.
 26. Ousaadi M, Merouane F, Berkani M, Almomani F, Vasseghian Y, Kitouni M. 2021. Valorization and optimization of agro-industrial orange waste for the production of enzyme by halophilic *Streptomyces* sp. *Environ. Res.* **201**: 111494.
 27. Gupta N, Paul JS, Jadhav SK. 2024. Biovalorizing agro-waste 'de-oiled rice bran' for thermostable, alkalophilic and detergent stable α -amylase production with its application as laundry detergent additive and textile desizer. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **256**: 128470.
 28. Veerakumar S, Manian R. 2022. Agarase, amylase and xylanase from *Halomonas meridiana*: A study on optimization of coproduction for biomass saccharification. *Fermentation* **8**: 479.
 29. Wu G, Qin Y, Cheng Q, Liu Z. 2014. Characterization of a novel alkali-stable and salt-tolerant α -amylase from marine bacterium *Zunongwangia profunda*. *J. Mol. Catal. B Enzym.* **110**: 8-15.
 30. Li Q, Yi L, Marek P, Iverson BL. 2013. Commercial proteases: present and future. *FEBS Lett.* **587**: 1155-1163.
 31. Yang X, Wang Z, Zhang C, Wang L, Pang L, Zhang D, et al. 2021. Assessment of the production of *Bacillus cereus* protease and its effect on the quality of ultra-high temperature-sterilized whole milk. *J. Dairy Sci.* **104**: 6577-6587.
 32. Mahakhan P, Apiso P, Srisunthorn K, Vichitphan K, Vichitphan S, Punyauppa-Path S, et al. 2023. Alkaline protease production from *Bacillus gibsonii* 6BS15-4 using dairy effluent and its characterization as a laundry detergent additive. *J. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **33**: 195-202.
 33. Rejisha RP, Murugan M. 2021. Alkaline protease production by halophilic *Bacillus* sp. strain SP II-4 and characterization with special reference to contact lens cleansing. *Mater. Today Proc.* **45**: 1757-1760.
 34. Bose A, Chawdhary V, Keharia H. 2014. Production and characterization of a solvent-tolerant protease from a novel marine isolate *Bacillus tequilensis* P15. *Ann. Microbiol.* **64**: 343-354.
 35. Delgado-garcía M, Flores-gallegos AC, Kirchmayr M, Rodríguez JA, Mateos-díaz JC, Aguilar CN, et al. 2019. Bioprospection of proteases from *Halobacillus andaensis* for bioactive peptide production from fish muscle protein. *Electron. J. Biotechnol.* **39**: 52-60.
 36. Sana B, Ghosh D, Saha M, Mukherjee J. 2006. Purification and characterization of a salt, solvent, detergent and bleach tolerant protease from a new gamma-*Proteobacterium* isolated from the marine environment of the Sundarbans. *Process Biochem.* **41**: 208-215.
 37. Gaonkar SK, Furtado IJ. 2020. Characterization of extracellular protease from the haloarcheon *Halococcus* sp. strain GUGFAWS-3 (MF425611). *Curr. Microbiol.* **77**: 1024-1034.
 38. Maharaja P, Boopathy R, Anushree VV, Mahesh M, Swarnalatha S, Ravindran B. 2020. Bio removal of proteins, lipids and mucopolysaccharides in tannery hyper saline wastewater using halophilic bacteria. *J. Water Process Eng.* **38**: 101674.
 39. Chandra P, Enespa, Singh R, Arora PK. 2020. Microbial lipases and their industrial applications: A comprehensive review. *Microb. Cell Fact.* **19**: 1-42.
 40. Qiu J, Han R, Wang C. 2021. Microbial halophilic lipases: A review. *J. Basic Microbiol.* **61**: 594-602.
 41. Li PY, Zhang YQ, Zhang Y, Jiang WX, Wang YJ, Zhang YS, et al. 2020. Study on a novel cold-active and halotolerant monoacylglycerol lipase widespread in marine bacteria reveals a new group of bacterial monoacylglycerol lipases containing unusual C(A/S)HSMG catalytic motifs. *Front. Microbiol.* **11**: 498595.
 42. Martínez-Pérez RB, Rodríguez JA, Cira-Chávez LA, Dendooven L, Viniegra-González G, Estrada-Alvarado I. 2020. Exoenzyme-producing halophilic bacteria from the former Lake Texcoco: identification and production of n-butyl oleate and bioactive peptides. *Folia Microbiol. (Praha)* **65**: 835-847.
 43. Yuan D, Lan D, Xin R, Yang B, Wang Y. 2014. Biochemical properties of a new cold-active mono- and diacylglycerol lipase from marine member *Janibacter* sp. strain HTCC2649. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **15**: 10554-10566.
 44. Kanlayakrit W, Boonpan A. 2007. Screening of halophilic lipase-producing bacteria and characterization of enzyme for fish sauce quality improvement. *Agric. Nat. Resour.* **41**: 576-585.
 45. Perez D, Martin S, Fernandez-Lorente G, Filice M, Guisán JM, Ventosa A, et al. 2011. A novel halophilic lipase, LipBL, showing high efficiency in the production of eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA). *PLoS One* **6**: e23325.
 46. Kiran GS, Lipton AN, Kennedy J, Dobson ADW, Selvin J. 2014. A halotolerant thermostable lipase from the marine bacterium *Oceanobacillus* sp. PUMB02 with an ability to disrupt bacterial biofilms. *Bioengineered* **5**: 305.
 47. Delgado-García M, Valdivia-Urdiales B, Aguilar-González CN, Contreras-Esquivel JC, Rodríguez-Herrera R. 2012. Halophilic hydrolases as a new tool for the biotechnological industries. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* **92**: 2575-2580.
 48. Khmaissa M, Hadrich B, Chamkha M, Sayari A, Fendri A. 2022. Production of a halotolerant lipase from *Halomonas* sp. strain C2SS100: Optimization by response-surface methodology and application in detergent formulations. *J. Surfactants Deterg.* **25**:

- 361-376.
49. Rajaei-Maleki S, Seyedalipour B, Ahmady-Asbchin S, Riazi G. 2021. Production of lipase by isolated halophile, *Halobacillus* sp. strain AR11 from International Miankaleh wetland. *J. Gene. Resour.* **7**: 188-195.
 50. Musa H, Kasim FH, Gunny AAN, Gopinath SCB, Ahmad MA. 2018. Biosecretion of higher halophilic lipase by a novel *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* AIKK2 using agro-waste as supporting substrate. *Process Biochem.* **72**: 55-62.
 51. Saranik MM, Badawy MA, Farahat MG. 2023. Fabrication of β -glucosidase-copper phosphate hybrid nanoflowers for bioconversion of geniposide into gardenia blue. *Int. J. Nanosci.* **22**: 2350040.
 52. Goyal K, Selvakumar P, Hayashi K. 2001. Characterization of a thermostable β -glucosidase (BglB) from *Thermotoga maritima* showing transglycosylation activity. *J. Mol. Catal. B Enzym.* **15**: 45-53.
 53. Khan S, Pozzo T, Megyeri M, Lindahl S, Sundin A, Turner C, et al. 2011. Aglycone specificity of *Thermotoga neapolitana* β -glucosidase 1A modified by mutagenesis, leading to increased catalytic efficiency in quercetin-3-glucoside hydrolysis. *BMC Biochem.* **12**: 11.
 54. Turner P, Svensson D, Adlercreutz P, Karlsson EN. 2007. A novel variant of *Thermotoga neapolitana* β -glucosidase B is an efficient catalyst for the synthesis of alkyl glucosides by transglycosylation. *J. Biotechnol.* **130**: 67-74.
 55. Qu X, Ding B, Li J, Liang M, Du L, Wei Y, et al. 2020. Characterization of a GH3 halophilic β -glucosidase from *Pseudoalteromonas* and its NaCl-induced activity toward isoflavones. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **164**: 1392-1398.
 56. Bhatia Y, Mishra S, Bisaria VS, Bhatia Y, Mishra S, Bisaria VS. 2008. Microbial β -glucosidases : Cloning, properties, and applications. *Crit. Rev. Biotechnol.* **22**: 375-407.
 57. de Veras BO, dos Santos YQ, Diniz KM, Carelli GSC, dos Santos EA. 2018. Screening of protease, cellulase, amylase and xylanase from the salt-tolerant and thermostable marine *Bacillus subtilis* strain SR60. *F1000Res* **7**: 1704.
 58. Ilesanmi Ol, Adekunle AE, Omolaiye JA, Olorode EM, Ogunkanmi AL. 2020. Isolation, optimization and molecular characterization of lipase producing bacteria from contaminated soil. *Sci. Afr.* **8**: e00279.
 59. Abd El-Ghany MN, Hamdi SA, Korany SM, Elbaz RM, Farahat MG. 2023. Biosynthesis of novel tellurium nanorods by *Gayadomonas* sp. TNPM15 isolated from mangrove sediments and assessment of their impact on spore germination and ultrastructure of phytopathogenic Fungi. *Microorganisms* **11**: 558.
 60. Marhuenda-Egea FC, Bonete MJ. 2002. Extreme halophilic enzymes in organic solvents. *Curr. Opin Biotechnol.* **13**: 385-389.
 61. Sigliocolo A, Paiardini A, Piscitelli M, Pascarella S. 2011. Structural adaptation of extreme halophilic proteins through decrease of conserved hydrophobic contact surface. *BMC Struct. Biol.* **11**: 1-12.
 62. Baati H, Bahloul M, Amdouni R, Azri C. 2022. Behavior assessment of moderately halophilic *Bacteria* in brines highly enriched with heavy metals: Sfax solar saltern (Tunisia), A Case Study. *Geomicrobiol. J.* **39**: 341-351.
 63. Rathakrishnan D, Gopalan AK. 2022. Isolation and characterization of halophilic isolates from Indian salterns and their screening for production of hydrolytic enzymes. *Environmental Challenges* **6**: 100426.
 64. Boujida N, Char S, El N, Manresa A, Miñana-galbis D, Skali N, et al. 2018. Biocatalysis and Agricultural Biotechnology Isolation and characterization of halophilic bacteria producing exopolymers with emulsifying and antioxidant activities. *Biocatal. Agric. Biotechnol.* **16**: 631-637.
 65. Nour A, Saibi E, Nas F, Arab M, Aissaoui N, Boukeroui Y, et al. 2022. Antimicrobial and enzymatic profiling of halophilic and halotolerant bacteria from a hypersaline lake 'The Great Sebkhah of Oran, Northwestern Algeria'. *Geomicrobiol. J.* **39**: 816-831.
 66. Villanova V, Galasso C, Fiorini F, Lima S, Br M, Sansone C, et al. 2021. Biological and chemical characterization of new isolated halophilic microorganisms from saltern ponds of Trapani, Sicily. *Algal Res.* **54**: 102192.
 67. Karray F, Ben M, Najwa A, Manel K, Manel H, Sami F. 2018. Extracellular hydrolytic enzymes produced by halophilic bacteria and archaea isolated from hypersaline lake. *Mol. Biol. Rep.* **45**: 1297-1309.
 68. Wang X, Zhao Y, Tan H, Chi N, Zhang Q, Du Y, et al. 2014. Characterisation of a chitinase from *Pseudoalteromonas* sp. DL-6, a marine psychrophilic bacterium. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **70**: 455-462.
 69. Boyadzhieva I, Tomova I, Radchenkova N, Kambourova M, Poli A, Vasileva-tonkova E. 2018. Diversity of heterotrophic halophilic bacteria isolated from coastal solar salterns, Bulgaria and their ability to synthesize bioactive molecules with biotechnological impact. *Microbiology* **87**: 519-528.
 70. Baati H, Amdouni R, Gharsallah N. 2010. Isolation and characterization of moderately halophilic bacteria from Tunisian solar saltern. *Curr. Microbiol.* **60**: 157-161.
 71. Sabet S, Diallo L, Hays L, Jung W, Dillon JG. 2009. Characterization of halophiles isolated from solar salterns in Baja California, Mexico. *Extremophiles* **13**: 643-656.
 72. Manikandan M, Kannan V, Pašić L. 2009. Diversity of microorganisms in solar salterns of Tamil Nadu, India. *World J. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **25**: 1007-1017.
 73. López-hermoso C, Haba RR De, Sánchez-porro C, Ventosa A. 2018. *Salinivibrio kushneri* sp. nov., a moderately halophilic bacterium isolated from salterns. *Syst. Appl. Microbiol.* **41**: 159-166.
 74. Toker SK, Evlat H, Koçyiğit A. 2021. Screening of newly isolated marine-derived fungi for their laccase production and decolorization of different dye types. *Reg. Stud. Mar. Sci.* **45**: 101837.
 75. Zhu D, Qaria MA, Zhu B, Sun J, Yang B. 2022. Extremophiles and extremozymes in lignin bioprocessing. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **157**: 112069.
 76. Amoozegar MA, Malekzadeh F, Malik KA. 2003. Production of amylase by newly isolated moderate halophile, *Halobacillus* sp.

- strain MA-2. *J. Microbiol. Methods* **52**: 353-359.
77. Wang X, Kan G, Shi C, Xie Q, Ju Y, Wang R, et al. 2019. Purification and characterization of a novel wild-type α -amylase from Antarctic sea ice bacterium *Pseudoalteromonas* sp. M175. *Protein Expr. Purif.* **164**: 105444.
 78. Kalpana BJ, Pandian SK. 2014. Halotolerant, acid-alkali stable, chelator resistant and raw starch digesting α -amylase from a marine bacterium *Bacillus subtilis* S8-18. *J. Basic Microbiol.* **54**: 802-811.
 79. Chakrabortya S, Khopadea A, Kokarea C, Mahadika K, Mahadik K. 2009. Isolation and characterization of novel α -amylase from marine *Streptomyces* sp. D1. *J. Mol. Catal. B Enzym.* **58**: 17-23.
 80. Najafi MF, Kembhavi A. 2005. One step purification and characterization of an extracellular α -amylase from marine *Vibrio* sp. *Enzyme Microb. Technol.* **36**: 535-539.
 81. Jianguo L, Zhiqiang Z, Hongyue D, Jianren L, Zhanfeng C. 2011. Isolation and characterization of a cold-active amylase from marine *Wangia* sp. C52. *Afr. J. Microbiol. Res.* **5**: 1156-1162.
 82. Mageswari A, Subramanian P, Chandrasekaran S. 2012. Optimization and immobilization of amylase obtained from halotolerant bacteria isolated from solar salterns. *J. Genet. Eng. Biotechnol.* **10**: 201-208.
 83. Chakraborty S, Jana S, Gandhi A, Sen KK, Zhiang W, Kokare C. 2014. Gellan gum microspheres containing a novel α -amylase from marine *Nocardiopsis* sp. strain B2 for immobilization. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **70**: 292-299.
 84. Kikani BA, Singh SP. 2012. The stability and thermodynamic parameters of a very thermostable and calcium-independent α -amylase from a newly isolated bacterium, *Anoxybacillus beppuensis* TSSC-1. *Process Biochem.* **47**: 1791-1798.
 85. Sanchez-Porro C, Mellado E, Bertoldo C, Antranikian G, Ventosa A. 2003. Screening and characterization of the protease CP1 produced by the moderately halophilic bacterium *Pseudoalteromonas* sp. strain CP76. *Extremophiles* **7**: 221-228.
 86. Ghoreishi FS, Roghanian R, Emtiazi G. 2020. Inhibition of quorum sensing-controlled virulence factors with natural substances and novel protease, obtained from *Halobacillus karajensis*. *Microb. Pathog.* **149**: 104555.
 87. Chamroensaksri N, Akaracharanya A, Visessanguan W, Tanasupawat S. 2007. Characterization of halophilic bacterium NB2-1 from PLA-RA and its protease production. *J. Food Biochem.* **32**: 536-555.
 88. Sinha R, Khare SK. 2012. Isolation of a halophilic *Virgibacillus* sp. EMB13: characterization of its protease for detergent application. *Indian J. Biotechnol.* **11**: 416-426.
 89. Daoud L, Jlidi M, Hmani H, Hadj Brahim A, El Arbi M, Ben Ali M. 2017. Characterization of thermo-solvent stable protease from *Halobacillus* sp. CJ4 isolated from Chott Eldjerid hypersaline lake in Tunisia. *J. Basic Microbiol.* **57**: 104-113.
 90. Sinsuwan S, Rodtong S, Yongsawatdigul J. 2010. A NaCl-stable serine proteinase from *Virgibacillus* sp. SK33 isolated from Thai fish sauce. *Food Chem.* **119**: 573-579.
 91. Xin L, Hui-Ying Y, Xiao-Xue L, Xiao S. 2011. Production and characterization of a novel extracellular metalloproteinase by a newly isolated moderate halophile, *Halobacillus* sp. LY6. *Folia Microbiol (Praha)* **56**: 329-334.
 92. de Lourdes Moreno M, Garcia MT, Ventosa A, Mellado E. 2009. Characterization of *Salicola* sp. IC10, a lipase-and protease-producing extreme halophile. *FEMS Microbiol. Ecol.* **68**: 59-71.
 93. Yang J, Li J, Mai Z, Tian X, Zhang S. 2013. Purification, characterization, and gene cloning of a cold-adapted thermolysin-like protease from *Halobacillus* sp. SCSIO 20089. *J. Biosci. Bioeng.* **115**: 628-632.
 94. Delgado-garcía M, Flores-gallegos AC, Kirchmayr M, Rodríguez JA, Mateos-díaz JC, Aguilar CN, et al. 2019. Bioprospection of proteases from *Halobacillus andensis* for bioactive peptide production from fish muscle protein. *Electron. J. Biotechnol.* **39**: 52-60.
 95. Jain D, Pancha I, Mishra SK, Shrivastav A, Mishra S. 2012. Purification and characterization of haloalkaline thermoactive, solvent stable and SDS-induced protease from *Bacillus* sp.: a potential additive for laundry detergents. *Bioresour. Technol.* **115**: 228-236.
 96. Annamalai N, Rajeswari MV, Sahu SK, Balasubramanian T. 2014. Purification and characterization of solvent stable, alkaline protease from *Bacillus firmus* CAS 7 by microbial conversion of marine wastes and molecular mechanism underlying solvent stability. *Process Biochem.* **49**: 1012-1019.
 97. Cui H, Wang L, Yu Y, others. 2015. Production and characterization of alkaline protease from a high yielding and moderately halophilic strain of SD11 marine bacteria. *J. Chem.* **2015**. ID 798304.
 98. Sanchez-Porro, Mellado E, Ventosa A, Martin S. 2003. Diversity of moderately halophilic bacteria producing extracellular hydrolytic enzymes. *J. Appl. Microbiol.* **94**: 295-300.
 99. Hemamalini R, Khare SK. 2018. Halophilic lipase does forms catalytically active aggregates: Evidence from *Marinobacter* sp. EMB5 lipase (LipEMB5). *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **119**: 172-179.
 100. Lopes EM, Fernandes CC, Lemos EGDM, Kishi LT. 2020. Reconstruction and in silico analysis of new *Marinobacter adhaerens* t76_800 with potential for long-chain hydrocarbon bioremediation associated with marine environmental lipases. *Mar. Genomics* **49**: 100685.
 101. Li X, Yu H-Y. 2014. Characterization of an organic solvent-tolerant lipase from *Haloarcula* sp. G41 and its application for biodiesel production. *Folia Microbiol (Praha)* **59**: 455-463.
 102. Charoenpanich J, Suktanarag S, Toobbucha N. 2011. Production of a thermostable lipase by *Aeromonas* sp. EBB-1 isolated from marine sludge in Angsila, Thailand. *Sci. Asia* **37**: 105-114.
 103. Mohan TS, Palavesam A, Ajitha RL. 2012. Optimization of lipase production by *Vibrio* sp.-A fish gut isolate. *Eur. J. Zool. Res.* **1**: 23-25.
 104. Su JH, Chang MC, Lee YS, Tseng IC, Chuang YC. 2004. Cloning and characterization of the lipase and lipase activator protein from *Vibrio vulnificus* CKM-1. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta* **1678**: 7-13.
 105. Sathishkumar R, Ananthan G, Iyappan K, Stalin C. 2015. A statis-

- tical approach for optimization of alkaline lipase production by ascidian associated—*Halobacillus trueperi* RSK CAS9. *Biotechnol. Rep.* **8**: 64-71.
106. Dueramae S, Bovornreungroj P, Enomoto T, Kantachote D. 2017. Purification and characterization of an extracellular lipolytic enzyme from the fermented fish-originated halotolerant bacterium, *Virgibacillus alimentarius* LBU20907. *Chem. Papers* **71**: 1975-1984.
 107. Cai L, Xu S, Lu T, Lin D, Yao S. 2019. Directed expression of halophilic and acidophilic β -glucosidases by introducing homologous constitutive expression cassettes in marine *Aspergillus niger*. *J. Biotechnol.* **292**: 12-22.
 108. Behera BC, Sethi BK, Mishra RR, Dutta SK, Thatoi HN. 2017. Microbial cellulases - Diversity & biotechnology with reference to mangrove environment: A review. *J. Genet. Eng. Biotechnol.* **15**: 197-210.
 109. Santos DA, Oliveira MM, Aprigio A, Curvelo S, Fonseca LP. 2017. Hydrolysis of cellulose from sugarcane bagasse by cellulases from marine-derived fungi strains. *Int. Biodeterior. Biodegradation* **121**: 66-78.
 110. Sukharnikov LO, Cantwell BJ, Podar M, Zhulin IB. 2011. Cellulases: ambiguous nonhomologous enzymes in a genomic perspective. *Trends Biotechnol.* **29**: 473-479.